

CHIPPING FAILURE OF AUTOMOTIVE COATED FILM LAYERS AT LOW TEMPERATURES

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Abstract

An experimental simulation of chipping failure of automotive coated film layers is performed using a low temperature impact test system, where the two kinds of specimens with and without a chipping primer inserted into the intermediate coat are used. A steel ball projectile is struck on a target plate (specimen) put in a freezer, when ultra-high speed photographs of the projectile rebounding from the target plate and scattering fragments of the coated layers are taken. The crater-like damage of the impacted specimens is inspected using a digital microscope and a scanning electron microscope. The energy conversion in chipping failure process is also considered, from which an index for evaluating a resistance to a chipping failure is proposed. Low-temperature durability of the coated film layers with an inserted chipping primer is finally verified.

1 Introduction

A driving automobile is often hit by foreign objects such as stones or gravel spattered by its own or the preceding cars, when the body surface of the car is damaged and the coated layers are delaminated [1,2]. This type of failure is called chipping failure. The chipping failure is a critical issue particularly in the cold regions like Canada and North America where roads are sprinkled with snow-melting salts as anti-freezing agents. The chipping damage not only devalues cosmetic appearance of the body surface, but also it has the potential to cause corrosion of the steel substrate. Therefore, some preventive measures have been taken against the chipping failure in automobile

manufacturers. A current approach toward enhancing the resistance against the chipping failure is by inserting a ductile layer with low Young's modulus even at low temperatures called a chipping primer between the coated film layers.

The objective of the present paper is to evaluate a resistance of the coated film layers with an inserted chipping primer to chipping failure, in which durability of the coated layers at low temperatures is focused in particular. For this purpose, firstly an experimental simulation of automotive coated film layers is performed using a low temperature impact test system, where a small steel ball projectile is struck on a target plate, i.e., a specimen with or without a chipping primer put in a freezer. In the simulation, both of the impact and rebounding velocities of the projectile are measured and ultra-high speed photographs of the chipping failure process are taken. Secondly, the surface damage of the impacted specimen is inspected with a digital microscopy and also the through-the thickness damage with a scanning electron microscopy. Finally, from these results and physical considerations of the energy conversion in the chipping failure process, durability of the coated film layers at low temperatures is verified.

2 Experimental Simulation of Chipping Failure

2.1 Specimens

Automobile bodies are made from zinc or zinc alloy coated steel sheets which show a good corrosion resistance. In general, automotive coating system, i.e., coated film layers comprises an electro-coating primer (E-coat), which is electrodeposited on the steel substrate, a primer-surfacer, and a top coat consisting of both basecoat and clearcoat. The E coat prevents corrosion like iron rust and also the top coat does weathering and acid rain as well as it throws a luster on the body surface, while an intermediate coat with the primer surfacer plays an

Table 1. Coating system of specimens A and B

(μm)	Specimen A	Specimen B
Clear coat	40	40
Base coat	18	18
Primer surfacer	35	35
Chipping primer	-	4
E-coat	20	20
Total film thickness	113	117

important role in the chipping failure. Thus, in the present study, the two kinds of specimens with and without a chipping primer inserted into the intermediate coat are selected in order to verify the resistance to chipping failure. Table 1 shows the details of the coating system of the specimens A and B. Both specimens are rectangular plates with a dimension of 150mm \times 70mm and a thickness of 0.96mm.

2.2 Low Temperature Impact Test System

Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of a low temperature impact test system, which consists of a gas-gun type impact testing machine, a low temperature freezer, and an ultra-high speed camera unit. The impact testing machine is capable of firing a steel ball projectile having a diameter of 1.6 mm and a mass of 17.2 mg at a maximum velocity of about 400 m/s by releasing high-pressurized helium gas or air gas. The freezer has an operational temperature ranging from 0 °C to - 20 °C . A target plate (specimen), which is mounted in the fixture, is put in the freezer and struck normally to its surface by the projectile. Two kinds of ultra-high speed camera units are used here, one has 512 \times 512 pixels and the other 1280 \times 1024 ones, which are operated and controlled through a personal computer.

Fig.1. Low temperature impact test system

2.3 Test Conditions and Procedures

The cooling temperatures selected in this tests are 0 °C and -20 °C, for each of which the cooling times are 1 hour and 24 hours. Under these cooling conditions, the target plates mounted in the fixture inside the freezer are struck by the steel ball projectile at three kinds of impact velocities, i.e., 60 m/s (216 km/h), 80 m/s (288 km/h), and 100 m/s (360 km/h). The impact velocity of the projectile just before impact is measured by a velocity detector consisting of a fiber-optic sensors, oscilloscope, and a single pulse inverter. The rebounding velocity of the projectile after impact is calculated from its change in location on the consecutive images of the ultra-high speed photographs.

3 Evaluation Method of Chipping Resistance

3.1 Energy Conversion in Failure Process

Consider a steel ball projectile having a mass of M impinging on a target plate at an impact velocity of V_i and rebounding at a rebound velocity of V_R .

3.1.1 Penetrating Process

During a penetrating process of the projectile into the plate, the kinetic energy $(1/2)MV_i^2$ changes forms and, by the conservation of energy principle, it is equal to the total energy E_{chip} consumed in that process which consists of the following four kinds of energies:

$$E_{chip} = E_d + E_e + E_f + E_o \quad (1)$$

- E_d : Energy associated with crater damage creation
- E_e : Elastic deformation energy of coated layers and steel substrate
- E_f : Kinetic energy of scattering fragments of layers
- E_o : Dispersion energy associated with friction, stress waves et al.

In Eq.(1), since E_f and E_o are considered smaller compared to E_d and E_e , the former are negligible.

3.1.2 Rebounding Process

During a rebounding process of the projectile, the elastic deformation energy is assumed to be completely converted into the kinetic energy of that, and therefore we have $E_e = (1/2)MV_R^2$. From these discussion, the energy E_d associated with crater damage creation can be expressed as

$$E_d = (1/2)M(V_i^2 - V_R^2) \quad (2)$$

3.2 Index for Evaluating Chipping Resistance

The value of E_d gives the degree of the crater damage, i.e., the smaller the value is, the smaller the magnitude of the crater damage. On the other hand, since the sum of E_d and E_e remains constant for a constant impact velocity, the larger the E_e is, the smaller the magnitude of the crater damage. Therefore, we can regard E_d or E_e as an index for evaluating a chipping resistance that gives a potential resistance of coated film layers against a chipping failure. For example, in order to reduce the crater damage produced by a chipping failure, an increased value of E_e is required, which means we have such coated film layers that is capable of storing large elastic deformation energy. It is also well known that a storing capacity of elastic deformation energy decreases at low temperatures due to the brittlement of materials. From this, if a large value of E_e holds even at low temperatures, this assures low-temperature durability of the coated film layers. So, E_e also gives an index for evaluating a resistance to a chipping failure at low temperatures.

4 Results and Discussions

4.1 Crater Damage Creation Energy

Figure 2 shows the relationships between crater damage creation energy E_d and impact velocity V_i for the case of cooling time of 1 hour, which is almost the same for 24 hours. From this figure, E_d is found to increase with an increasing impact velocity. However, there is little difference between the values for two different cooling temperatures and specimens.

Fig.2. Crater damage energy vs. impact velocity

Fig.3. Digital micrographs of crater damage (Specimen A)

Fig.4. Digital micrographs of crater damage (Comparison of specimens A and B)

This indicates that the crater damage creation energy hardly varies up to a cooling temperature of -20°C at least. So, the inserted chipping primer affects little increase of a resistance against chipping failure.

4.2 Digital Micrographs of Crater Damage

Figure 3 shows digital micrographs of the crater damage produced in the specimen A by impact of three different impact velocities under a cooling condition of -20°C and 24 hours. The projective area of the crater damage, which is approximated by a circumscribed circle, is seen to increase with an increasing impact velocity. For the specimen B without a chipping primer, the corresponding damage area is not so large as that of the specimen A with an inserted chipping primer. In other words, the damage area found on the surface of the specimen A is larger compared to B under the same test condition.

Upper layers damaged/fractured , E-coat survived

(a) Specimen A

Zinc coat/E-coat delaminated , E-coat damaged

(b) Specimen B

Fig.5. SEM of impact-induced damage in through-the thickness section

Figure 4 also shows digital micrographs of the crater damages induced by impact at a cooling temperature of -20°C . It is seen that the projective areas of the craters make little difference for both specimens A and B.

4.3 SEM of Impact-Induced Damage in Through-The Thickness Section

Figure 5 shows SEM pictures of the impact-induced damage in the through-the thickness sections under a cooling condition of 0°C and 24 hours. In the case of specimen A, although the upper layers of the chipping primer are damaged or fractured, E-coat (electrocoating primer) is not damaged. However, for specimen B, E-coat is not only damaged and fractured, but also the zinc coated layer/ E-coat interface is delaminated. From these pictures, a chipping primer is found to suppress such a serious damage that reaches a steel substrate. Therefore, a chipping primer is proven to be effective in enhancing the resistance to chipping failure.

4.4 Evaluating Index for Chipping Resistance

The test results showed that the value of E_c for specimen A was smaller than that of specimen B, which agreed with the results obtained from the digital micrographs as mentioned in 4.2. This means that insertion of a chipping primer reduced a storing capacity of elastic deformation energy. On the other hand, as mentioned in 4.3, SEM shows that a chipping primer is effective in suppressing a serious damage arriving at a steel substrate.

5 Conclusions

Durability of automotive coated film layers currently used is studied by performing an experimental simulation of chipping failure at low temperatures, inspecting impact-induced damage through digital and electron scanning microscopy, and by considering energy conversion in that process. The effects of cooling temperatures, cooling times, and impact velocities on the crater-like damage due to a chipping failure are discussed, from which insertion of a chipping primer between coated film layers is proven to be effective in enhancing a chipping resistance and therefore low-temperature durability of the coated layers is verified.

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